

IAVS RESEARCH GROUP, NCSU

INVESTIGATORS AND CONSULTANTS (1984-1994)

Principle-Investigator	Discipline(s):	From:
Mark R. McMurtry, Ph.D.	Horticultural Science, Integrated Bio-production Systems, Environmental Design, International Development	1984
Co-Investigators:	Discipline(s):	
Edward A. Estes, Ph.D.	Agricultural and Aquacultural Economics	1988
Blanche C. Haning, Ph.D.	Integrated Pest Management and Plant Pathology	1986
Ronald G. Hodson, Ph.D.	Aquatic Ecosystems , Fisheries Management & Genetics	1986
Paul V. Nelson, Ph.D., FASHS	Botanical Mineral Nutrition & Greenhouse Management	1984
Robert P. Patterson, Ph.D., FCSSA	Agronomy, Soil Fertility, & Plant Physiology	1984
Douglas C. Sanders, Ph.D., FASHS	Horticultural Science and Plant Physiology	1986
Principle Consultants:	Discipline(s):	
J. Lawrence Apple, P.h.D.	International Development, Plant Pathology	1985
Marc A. Buchanan, Ph.D.	Agricultural Ecology and Soil Science	1985
Stanley W. Buol, Ph.D.	Geomorphology. Mineralogy and Soil Genesis	1985
JoAnn Burkholder, Ph.D., FAAAS	Phycology and Aquatic Ecology	1988
James E. Easley, Ph.D.	Aquacultural Economics and Business	1987
Donald Huisingh, Ph.D.	Ecology and Environmental Resource Recovery	1984
Merle H. Jensen, Ph.D.	Agricultural Program Development (UAZ ERL)	1985
Thomas Losordo, Ph.D.	Recirculatory Aquaculture	1987
L. George Wilson, Ph.D., FASHS	Horticultural Science and Extension	1988
Ad Hoc Consultants (partial):	Discipline(s):	
Peter Cooke, Ph.D.	Intensive Aquaculture Systems (Disney World, EPCOT)	1986
Barry A. Costa-Pierce, Ph.D. FAAAS	International Aquaculture Development (ICLARM)	1988
Robert Jack Downs, Ph.D.	Controlled Environment Agricultural Research	1986
Kevin Fittsimmons, Ph.D.	Intensive and Recirculatory Aquaculture (ERL)	1986
H. Douglas Gross, Ph.D.	Crop Science and International Agric. Development	1987
Larry D. King, Ph.D.	Sustainable (Low-input) Agricultural Systems	1986
John Lavine, D.V.M	Veterinary Medicine, <i>Cichlidae</i> spp. Specialist	1987
Michael Linker, Ph.D.	Entomology and Integrated Pest Management	1987
Steve Malvestuto, Ph.D.	Fisheries Assessment and Development	1988
George A. Marlowe, Ph.D.	Horticulture Research and Development (AVRDC)	1987
Robert H. Miller, Ph.D.	Soil Nutrition and Microbial Ecology	1987
Richard A. Neal, Ph.D.	International Aquaculture Development (USAID)	1986
Edward Noga, D.V.M	Veterinary Medicine, Aquatic vertebrates	1988
Glenn W. Patterson, Ph.D.	International Agro-Industries Development (ATI)	1988
Pedro A. Sanchez, Ph.D., FAAAS	Tropical Soils Management	1988
John C. Sager, Ph.D., FASABE	Controlled Environmental Life Support Systems (NASA)	1987
Ronald Sneed, Ph.D., FASABE	Agricultural Engineering, Irrigation Systems	1987
Kenneth Sorrenson, Ph.D.	Entomology and Greenhouse Pest Management	1987
Carolyn A. Williams, Ph.D.	Vegetable Horticulture and Physiology	1988
Other Technical Resources (partial):	Field:	
Reed Altman, M.S.	Aquaculture Development (US Peace Corps)	1988
Ray Campbell, Ph.D.	Plant Nutrition and Tissue Analysis (NCDA)	1985
Dale E. Ettl, Ph.D.	Fish Feed Formulation (Purina Mills, Inc.)	1987
Vincent M. Foote, FIDSA	Integrated Systems Design	1984
Nancy Mingus, M.S.	Plant Tissue Analysis	1987
Boone. M. Mora, D.V.M.	Commercial IAVS Demonstration project	1990
Brandy Noon, M.A.	Presentation and Graphics Design	1986
Stephen F. Pekkala, AIA	Architecture and Development Programming	1985
Martin L. Price, Ph.D.	Development Assistance and Networking (ECHO)	1988
Ray Tucker, Ph.D.	Soil Fertility and Analysis (NCDA)	1985